

How Managerial Skills, Teacher Empowerment, and Teacher Maturity Affect Principal Leadership: A Study in High Schools of North Tapanuli, Indonesia

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Article history:

Received: December 30, 2024; Accepted: February 01, 2025; Displayed Online: February 03, 2025; Published: June 30, 2025

Keywords

Managerial Competence;

Teacher Empowerment;

Teacher Maturity;

Leadership Effectiveness;

Abstract

This study examines the impact of managerial competence, teacher empowerment, and teacher maturity on the leadership effectiveness of senior high school principals in North Tapanuli, Indonesia. A sample of 665 teachers was randomly selected, and data were collected through a validated Likert scale questionnaire. The analysis revealed that: (1) Managerial competence significantly enhances leadership effectiveness ($p < 0.001$; $\text{Exp}(B) = 2.7$), (2) Teacher empowerment positively influences leadership ($p = 0.031$; $\text{Exp}(B) = 1.43$), and (3) Teacher maturity is the most significant factor affecting leadership effectiveness ($p = 0.031$; $\text{Exp}(B) = 3.44$). In summary, increased managerial competence, teacher empowerment, and teacher maturity lead to more effective leadership among principals.

1. Introduction

The principal is the driving force in efforts to improve the quality of education so that schools are expected to be able to make significant changes (Widodo, 2011). The success of an educational institution generally depends heavily on the leader in the institution. Schools, as complex organizations, require high coordination. Meanwhile, good coordination requires effective school leadership. Therefore, a successful principal is a principal who can coordinate all components, including human resources, to achieve school goals and the goals of individuals in the school environment.

A practical and successful principal is related to the level of concern of the leader for what has been achieved by the organization (organizational achievement) and coaching for the

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organization (organization maintenance) (Wahjosumidjo 2021). According to Rohiat, effective management can be possible if the manager has good management skills. Skills are intended to be able to manage the resources owned by the organization effectively and efficiently. In addition, these resources are not always available, so managers must try to provide them.

There are four managerial skills, namely: (1) conceptual skills, skills to understand and operate organizations. (2) Human skills, skills to work together; (3) technical skills, skills to use knowledge, methods, techniques, and equipment to complete tasks (4) design skills, the ability to solve problems and seek benefits for the organization (Rohiat 2019).

In the pre-research, the principal's managerial competence is generally not good in terms of conceptual competence, such as the lack of principals seeking opportunities, such as new ideas, to achieve goals by the vision and mission. Regarding personal communication competence, principals do not listen to teacher complaints and make activity schedules according to priorities. Another factor that influences the effectiveness of principal leadership is teacher empowerment. Idua believes employee empowerment contributes to organizational performance (Idua 2017). Empowerment causes increased internal work motivation, job satisfaction, work involvement inside and outside the work determined by responsibility, and low work-related stress (Menon 2001).

Choong et al., in their study, concluded that the four psychological empowerment cognitions, meaning, competence, self-determination, and its impact, are positively related to organizational performance (Choong, Wong, and Lau 2011). Employee empowerment is management participation that involves employees being responsible in their work process (Idua 2017).

The effectiveness of leadership is seen in the performance of teachers tasked with managing the teaching and learning process, such as increased teacher productivity and performance. Indications of increased teacher productivity due to teacher empowerment by the principal prove that the principal's leadership is effective. The results of pre-research related to teacher empowerment also found, among others, a lack of rewards or appreciation for the success obtained by a teacher and a lack of teacher involvement in thinking about strategies for achieving school goals by the vision. This indicates a lack of desire from the leader (principal) to delegate and involve teachers to achieve goals. The effectiveness of the principal's leadership is also influenced by teacher maturity.

Teacher maturity can be seen in two things, namely, job maturity and psychological maturity. According to Thoah, job maturity concerns or is associated with abilities, knowledge, and skills that can be obtained from education, training, and experience. Psychological maturity is related to self-confidence, readiness to accept responsibility, willingness, and motivation (Thoah 2006). Problems pertaining to teacher maturity include some teachers' lack of responsibility in work. This was revealed when conducting pre-research observations on the perception and philosophy of a teacher. Therefore, this study will try to explore the problem of the effectiveness of the leadership of the principal of State Senior High Schools in North Tapanuli, including the factors that influence it: Principal managerial competence, teacher empowerment, and teacher maturity.

2. Research Method

Bivariate Test

Based on the results of the Bivariate test of the influence of Managerial Competence on the Effectiveness of Principal Leadership, a study of 250 respondents showed that out of 131 respondents who answered that managerial competence was not good, 73 (55.7%) answered that leadership was not good and 58 (44.3%) answered that leadership effectiveness was good. Out of 119 respondents with good managerial competence answers, 24 (20.2%) answered that leadership effectiveness was not good, and 95 (79.8%) answered that leadership effectiveness

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was good. The results of the chi-square test were obtained ($p = <0.001$; Exp (B) = 2.7; 95% CI 1.873-4.076), meaning that there is an influence of managerial competence on the effectiveness of principal leadership. Principal leadership that is not good has a 2.7 times greater chance of having poor managerial competence than principal leadership with good leadership. So, the proposed hypothesis test criteria Reject the hypothesis H_0 if $p_value < \alpha = 5\%$. Then it can be concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted because based on the results of the chi-square test, it is known that the $p_value = 0.001 < \alpha = 5\%$

Based on the results of the Bivariate test of the influence of teacher empowerment on the Effectiveness of the principal's leadership, a study of 250 respondents showed that out of 114 respondents who answered that employee empowerment was not good, 53 people (46.5%) answered that leadership effectiveness was not good and 61 people (53.5%) answered that leadership effectiveness was good. Of 136 respondents with good teacher empowerment answers, 44 (32.4%) answered that leadership effectiveness was not good, and 92 (67.6%) answered that leadership effectiveness was good. The chi-square test results obtained ($p = 0.031$; Exp (B) = 1.43; 95% CI 1.051 - 1.965) mean that teacher empowerment influences the effectiveness of the principal's leadership. Poor principal leadership has a 1.43 times greater chance of teachers having poor empowerment than good principal leadership. By the proposed hypothesis test criteria, Reject the hypothesis H_0 if $p_value < \alpha = 5\%$. Then it can be concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted because based on the results of the chi-square test, it is known that the $p_value = 0.001 < \alpha = 5\%$

Based on the results of the Bivariate test of the influence of teacher maturity on the effectiveness of the principal's leadership, the study of 250 respondents showed that out of 132 respondents who answered that teacher maturity was not good, 77 people (58.3%) answered that leadership effectiveness was not good and 55 people (41.7%) answered that leadership effectiveness was good. Of the 118 respondents with good teacher maturity answers, 20 (16.9%) answered that leadership effectiveness was not good, and 98 (83.1%) answered that leadership effectiveness was good. The chi-square test results show a value ($p = 0.031$; Exp (B) = 3.44; 95% CI 2.251 - 5.262), meaning that teacher maturity influences the effectiveness of principal leadership. Poor principal leadership has a 3.44 times greater chance of teachers having poor teacher maturity than good principal leadership. By the proposed hypothesis test criteria, Reject the hypothesis H_0 if $p_value < \alpha = 5\%$, then it can be concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted because, based on the results of the chi-square test, it is known that the $p_value = 0.031 < \alpha = 5\%$.

Multivariate Test: Variable Selection in Logistic Regression Analysis

The variables included in the logistic regression test have a $p_value < 0.25$.

Table 1.
Results of Selection of Variables That Can Be Included in the Logistic Regression Model

No	Variable	<i>P value</i>	Fixed Value	Modeling
1	Managerial competence	<0,001	$p < 0,25$	Suitable
2	Teacher empowerment	0,022	$p < 0,25$	Suitable
3	Teacher maturity	<0,001	$p < 0,25$	Suitable

Table 1 shows that managerial competence, teacher empowerment, and teacher maturity have a p-value <0.25, so these variables are continued to the multivariate analysis stage. The results of the multivariate analysis are shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2.
Logistic Regression Model of Principal Leadership Effectiveness

Variable	Model 1 <i>p-value;Exp(β)(95%CI)</i>	Model 2 <i>p-value;Exp(β)(95%CI)</i>
Managerial competence	<0,001; 6,2 (3,251-11,829)	<0,001; 6,1 (3,218-11,638)
Teacher empowerment	0,572; 0,82 (0,428-1,597)	
Teacher maturity	<0,001; 8,8 (4,366-18,006)	<0,001; 8,2 (4,276-15,843)

Table 2 shows that the dominant variable influencing the effectiveness of principal leadership based on logistic regression analysis is the teacher maturity variable ($p = <0.001$; $\text{Exp}(\beta) = 8.2$; 95% CI 4.276-15.843), meaning that the teacher maturity variable is significant to the effectiveness of principal leadership. Poor principal leadership has an 8.2 times greater chance of teachers having poor teacher maturity than good principal leadership. By the proposed hypothesis test criteria, Reject the hypothesis H_0 if $p_value < \alpha = 5\%$. Then it can be concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted because, based on the results of the chi-square test, it is known that the $p_value = 0.001 < \alpha = 5\%$

3. Discussion

Based on the analysis of statistical calculation data and hypothesis testing, it has been proven that the four hypotheses proposed can be accepted as valid. About the results of the proof, a discussion of the results of the logistic regression test between variables is carried out as follows:

a. The Influence of Managerial Competence on the Effectiveness of Principal Leadership

Managerial competence is the ability to lead, manage, and coordinate organizational resources. This ability is essential, mainly because a manager must ensure that all team members can work effectively and efficiently to achieve the goals that have been set. To become a successful manager, a person must have good managerial skills. According to Suwatno (2019), a reliable leader is a leader who has several managerial competencies.

The competencies that the principal must possess are personality, managerial, entrepreneurial, supervision, and social. Given the tasks that must be carried out and the competencies that the principal must possess, the principal experiences various obstacles in realizing the quality of education in general and the quality of schools in particular (Suwanda 2018).

The study's results showed that managerial competence influences the effectiveness of the principal's leadership. Poor principal leadership has a 2.7 times greater chance of the principal having poor managerial competence than good principal leadership. This study aligns with previous research (Winaryo et al., 2016), which reported that the principal's managerial competence significantly affects school effectiveness and obtained a significance value ($p = 0.000$). The effectiveness of the principal's leadership will be visible if the principal can create conducive managerial competence and motivate his teachers to be willing and able to carry out all activities to achieve the school's vision, mission, and goals.

Another study also reported that the principal's competence and information systems positively affect school effectiveness; this means that the higher the principal's competence and

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the better the quality of the information system, the more effective the school will be (Lestari et al., 2023). The principal's leadership significantly positively affects teacher competence in realizing school effectiveness. School effectiveness can run well by implementing the principal's leadership and teacher competence (Banani 2022)

The principal's managerial ability is essential in developing schools or educational institutions. The principal must be able to manage the academic resources available in the school, including teaching and education personnel, facilities and infrastructure, curriculum, and opportunities for collaboration with related institutions. Good management of all these elements will create effective leadership to achieve the school's vision and mission.

b. The Influence of Teacher Empowerment on the Effectiveness of Principal Leadership

Richard L. Daft defines empowerment as releasing the power and creativity of employees by giving them the freedom, resources, information, and skills to make decisions effectively. According to him, empowering teachers involves at least four essential elements that allow employees to act freely in completing their work: 1. Employees receive information about company performance. Companies implementing employee empowerment provide full access to financial issues and operational information. 2. Employees have the knowledge and skills to contribute to company goals. The company holds training programs to help employees gain knowledge and skills to contribute to the company. 3. Employees have the authority to make decisions. Employees participate in every company meeting and every decision-making process. 4. Employees are rewarded based on their performance in the company. Employees are rewarded according to the performance shown. (Daft L Richard 2018) The results of this study indicate that teacher empowerment influences the effectiveness of principal leadership. Poor principal leadership has a 1.43 times greater chance of teachers having poor empowerment than good principal leadership. This study aligns with previous studies that reported a positive direct effect of empowerment and trust on the principal's responsibility (Suhardi, M, 2023).

Empowerment allows teachers to make decisions and complete their workload on time. Empowerment is not enough by building abilities and giving them opportunities to act; it is also related to values. Empowerment requires high honesty, openness, and integrity in top management. Thus, empowerment is not just a delegation from leaders to teachers in their organizations but is more about the value system in the adopted organization. Empowerment entrusts teachers to make decisions and take responsibility for their choices and actions (Lestari & Siregar, 2021; Resnadita, 2020; Saputra & Fermayani, 2019).

Some things that can be done to empower teachers include increasing work enthusiasm, building collaboration and cooperation, encouraging professional development, creating a conducive work environment, reward and punishment programs, etc. Teacher empowerment that is carried out properly provides confidence to develop teacher creativity so that teacher work professionalism will increase (Nadeak 2019).

Empowerment gives teachers the autonomy to make decisions and solve problems, encourages innovation, improves performance and productivity, and allows teachers to utilize their skills and knowledge optimally.

c. The Influence of Teacher Maturity on the Effectiveness of Principal Leadership

Teacher maturity is seen through ability and willingness. When people have reached maturity within themselves, they will expand their attention to the outside of themselves. The

more fully an individual is involved in various activities or ideas, the healthier they will be psychologically.

A mature self can accept all aspects of themselves, including weaknesses. It has emotional intelligence that allows individuals to control and not hide emotions. A mature and healthy self will be free from insecurity and fear. In addition, it is not easy to give up, and I will continue to look for ways to achieve my goals. The study's results showed that teacher maturity influenced the effectiveness of the principal's leadership. Poor principal leadership has a 3.44 times greater chance of teachers having poor teacher maturity than good principal leadership.

The study is in line with previous studies, namely that teacher maturity has the most outstanding value or influence on leadership effectiveness, so if teachers have adequate maturity in carrying out their work responsibilities, it will have a positive impact on leadership effectiveness (Nasution, IL et al., 2018). The study also states a significant influence between teacher maturity and organizational leadership effectiveness (Permaiswati, YC et al., 2015).

The study (Nuridin, 2012) shows the maturity of teachers in private junior high schools in Semarang City. A mature person views the world objectively, does not easily give trust to something, can accept reality without having to change reality to suit their desires, and is responsible for every job. Individuals with high self-understanding will be wise to others so that others can receive them well. Have plans prepared in the long term, have clear goals, and do tasks until finished. The characteristics of maturity, as described, will affect the effectiveness of leadership in schools.

d. The influence of simultaneous logistic regression test results

The results of simultaneous testing of managerial competence, teacher empowerment, and teacher maturity on the effectiveness of principal leadership show that the most significant influence on the effectiveness of principal leadership is teacher maturity. Poor principal leadership has an 8.2 times greater chance of teachers having poor subordinate maturity compared to good principal leadership. This is in line with research (Nuridin, 2012) that shows that subordinate maturity significantly affects the effectiveness of the principal's leadership style.

One key factor for leadership effectiveness is identifying the level of maturity of individuals or groups to be influenced to use the appropriate leadership style. Maturity in situational leadership can be formulated as a person's ability and willingness to be responsible for directing their behavior. The concept of maturity, in its relationship, consists of ability and desire (Permaiswati, YC, 2015). According to Thoha (2013:68), job maturity concerns or is associated with the ability, knowledge, and skills obtained from experience.

A leader's role in managing subordinates is vital because leadership influences others to achieve goals. Therefore, the process of managing human resources must be accompanied by an understanding of the level of maturity of subordinates to create conditions where a leader can manage his subordinates appropriately so that subordinates can be more productive in working (Anggoro, DD. et al. 2012)

4. Conclusion

Managerial competence directly affects principal leadership effectiveness at State Senior High Schools in North Tapanuli. This means that increasing managerial competence causes an increase in the effectiveness of principal leadership. In other words, the higher the managerial competence of State Senior High Schools in North Tapanuli, the higher the effectiveness of the principal's leadership. The results of this study conclude that H_a is accepted. Several things that the principal has not optimally done are developing strategies in achieving the school's Vision, determining technicalities in implementing programs, utilizing and utilizing facilities in

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implementing programs, using equipment needed to support special activities, and making decisions based on various information.

Teacher empowerment directly affects the effectiveness of principal leadership at State Senior High Schools in North Tapanuli. This means that effective teacher empowerment will impact the effectiveness of the principal's leadership. In other words, the higher the teacher empowerment, the higher the effectiveness of the principal's leadership. The results of this study conclude that H_a is accepted. Some things in the teacher empowerment variable that still have relatively small scores and are in the category of being done less often or only sometimes are that the principal has not trained teachers to be able to supervise themselves or teachers have the self-awareness to carry out tasks responsibly; the principal has not given awards or rewards for the success achieved by a teacher, has not explored ideas and suggestions from teachers and built trust between the principal and teachers.

Teacher maturity directly affects the effectiveness of the leadership of the principal of State Senior High Schools in North Tapanuli. Good teacher maturity will increase the effectiveness of the principal's leadership. In other words, the higher a teacher's maturity level, the more effective the principal's leadership.

The results of this study conclude that H_a is accepted. Things that a teacher still lacks related to maturity are less involvement in activities outside the main activities, less objectivity in assessing others, and less awareness of shortcomings. However, teacher maturity is the most significant indicator influencing the effectiveness of the leadership of the principal of State Senior High Schools in North Tapanuli.

Acknowledgment

This manuscript has no conflict of interest. The authors deliver their gratitude to all parties who have contributed to this publication of the manuscript.

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